

MULTIFLOW: Shifting Towards Task-Agnostic Vision-Language Pruning

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Abstract

While excellent in transfer learning, Vision-Language models (VLMs) come with high computational costs due to their large number of parameters. To address this issue, removing parameters via model pruning is a viable solution. However, existing techniques for VLMs are task-specific, and thus require pruning the network from scratch for each new task of interest. In this work, we explore a new direction: Task-Agnostic Vision-Language Pruning (TA-VLP). Given a pretrained VLM, the goal is to find a unique pruned counterpart transferable to multiple unknown downstream tasks. In this challenging setting, the transferable representations already encoded in the pretrained model are a key aspect to preserve. Thus, we propose Multimodal Flow Pruning (MULTIFLOW), a first, gradient-free, pruning framework for TA-VLP where: (i) the importance of a parameter is expressed in terms of its magnitude and its information flow, by incorporating the saliency of the neurons it connects; and (ii) pruning is driven by the emergent (multimodal) distribution of the VLM parameters after pretraining. We benchmark eight state-of-the-art pruning algorithms in the context of TA-VLP, experimenting with two VLMs, three vision-language tasks, and three pruning ratios. Our experimental results show that MULTIFLOW outperforms recent sophisticated, combinatorial competitors in the vast majority of the cases, paving the way towards addressing TA-VLP. The code is publicly available at <https://github.com/FarinaMatteo/multiflow>.

1. Introduction

Large-scale vision-language models (VLMs) [38–40, 53] show remarkable transfer learning capabilities and achieve state-of-the-art results in multiple vision-language tasks after fine-tuning with task-specific data and little architectural changes. However, these practical advantages come at the price of a huge number of parameters, e.g., in the

Figure 1. The conceptual difference between existing VLM pruning methods [58, 65] and our proposed Task-Agnostic Vision-Language Pruning. While existing pruning methods use task-specific knowledge, hence requiring pruning the dense model from scratch for different tasks, we propose to shift the perspective and formalize TA-VLP, which only requires pruning once.

order of hundreds of millions [39], hindering deployment in memory-constrained devices. A solution to this problem is to reduce the network size via pruning [23], a compression technique whose aim is to explicitly remove network parameters. In the context of VLMs, existing approaches perform pruning for specific downstream tasks [58, 65], where the obtained pruned models achieve good transfer learning performance once fine-tuned. Critically, this requires re-pruning the model from scratch if the downstream task changes. This is not only time-consuming, but fur-

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ther assumes that the original VLM parameters can easily be stored. To overcome these issues, we tackle the problem from a different perspective, investigating the possibility of pruning a VLM while maintaining its general transfer learning capabilities. Towards this goal, we propose Task-Agnostic Vision-Language Pruning (TA-VLP), where the aim is to prune a VLM *once* and obtain a sparse model transferable to multiple *unknown* tasks when fine-tuned (see Fig. 1). While appealing, finding an optimal solution to TA-VLP is challenging as we cannot use any task-specific priors nor feedback during pruning, and different downstream tasks may focus on different visual/linguistic cues (*e.g.*, local for visual question answering, global for captioning). Nevertheless, we can still rely on one anchor: the pretrained VLM. In fact, pretraining uses a generic objective, such as vision-language alignment, which applied to large-scale data enables learning generic and transferable representations. These representations depend on the network parameters and on how the (multimodal) activations propagate through the network. Intuitively, if we assume the pretrained model to be transferable, its pruned counterpart should preserve the learned activation patterns.

Following this principle, we propose Multimodal Flow Pruning (MULTIFLOW), a first method for TA-VLP. MULTIFLOW models each layer as a bipartite graph, where nodes are activations and edges are parameters. Exploiting calibration data, the saliency of a parameter is modeled by combining its magnitude with the average signal emitted/aggregated by the input/output nodes it connects. However, directly pruning using these scores may lead to biases w.r.t. the depth of a layer, and ignores that activation patterns and magnitudes may differ among modalities. To overcome this issue, we disentangle modalities and guide pruning with the emergent distribution of the magnitude of the parameters. Our experiments on XVLM [71] and BLIP [39], with three vision-language tasks and pruning ratios, show that MULTIFLOW consistently matches or surpasses existing methods while requiring no gradient information.

Contributions. To summarize, our contributions are:

- We formalize Task-Agnostic Vision-Language Pruning, whose aim is to prune a VLM *once* while maintaining transferability to *unknown* downstream tasks.
- We propose Multimodal Flow Pruning, a first specific method for TA-VLP, where the importance of a parameter depends on the aggregated importance of the nodes it connects and its magnitude, exploiting multimodal priors to guide the distribution of each layer and avoid biases.
- We benchmark existing methods and MULTIFLOW on TA-VLP, with multiple vision-language tasks, VLMs, and pruning ratios, demonstrating the effectiveness of MULTIFLOW. These results and the proposed benchmark also highlight a large gap w.r.t. the performance of the dense model, paving the way for future research on this topic.

2. Related Work

Post-training pruning. Several works remove parameters after training [16, 26–28, 35, 36], aiming to reduce inference time [47, 48] and storage requirements [21, 72]. While some of these techniques are data-free and mostly rely on weight magnitude, others are data-driven and exploit first- or second-order information. Another line of data-driven algorithms relies on combinatorial optimization [4, 59, 69] or iterative procedures, like iterative magnitude pruning (IMP) [18, 55], which alternates training until convergence, magnitude pruning, and weight rewinding. While we also exploit the weight magnitude in our pruning criterion, we additionally consider how information propagates through the target VLMs, fostering transferability to *unknown* tasks.

Pruning at initialization. Since our goal is to prune the model *before* fine-tuning it on downstream tasks, our work is also closely related to pruning at initialization (PaI). PaI methods rely on a *saliency* function that evaluates each connection, removing those with the lowest saliency scores to meet a target sparsity level [1, 8, 37]. Notably, the same saliency scores can be re-used for different sparsity targets without any additional computational overhead. The saliency function can also be applied iteratively, trading-off efficiency for performance [52, 61, 68]. PaI methods can be categorized based on their input as well, with data-dependent algorithms [1, 8, 37, 52] employing samples from the target dataset, and data-free techniques using synthetic inputs [61, 68]. Our work shares the same rationale of these techniques, *i.e.*, the saliency of network connections is central to our pruning strategy. However, while existing PaI methods mostly focus on task-specific objectives with backward gradient propagation, MULTIFLOW is gradient-free, as it is only based on the forward function of the model.

Pruning in Vision and/or Language. Several works explore pruning in the context of vision and language, with works sparsifying large pretrained models in NLP, *e.g.*, BERT [29, 33, 34, 70], GPT [20] and LLaMA [60], and vision transformers [17], *e.g.*, via model [29, 36, 67, 73] or token [5, 41, 45, 54, 62] pruning. To the best of our knowledge, UPop [58] and EfficientVLM [65] are the only pruning algorithms specifically developed and benchmarked on multiple vision-language tasks. The former progressively prunes the target VLM during fine-tuning, while the latter is a distill-then-prune framework. However, both methods require task-specific knowledge *by design*. In this work, we take instead a different direction, investigating how we can extract task-agnostic subnetworks from VLMs.

Unimodal Task-Agnostic Pruning. In the context of Vision- or Language-only, some works already explored the ability of pruned models to generalize to multiple tasks [66]. For instance, [10, 12] assess that the *train-prune-retrain* paradigm of IMP can also be successfully applied during

unimodal pretraining. In principle, a task-agnostic subnetwork can also emerge when pretraining by optimizing the pruning masks as trainable parameters (a common procedure in continual learning [44] or neural architecture search [9]), as shown in [43]. However, complete access to the pretraining phase is often out of reach due to its large computational demand. Exploratory works also study the effects of pruning on BERT transfer [24], highlighting that finetuning recovers dense performance when less than half of the parameters are pruned, or on self-supervised CNNs [6].

Our work has different rationales. Motivated by [23], which showcases the additional difficulty in finding task-agnostic pruned models with Vision and Language w.r.t. unimodal scenarios, we design the first algorithm for TA-VLP. We do not assume access to large amounts of data nor the pretraining phase, striving for *fast* and *efficient* pruning. Hence, we avoid the burden of both computing and storing gradients for large VLMs with a gradient-free algorithm. Neither IMP nor Mask Training meet these principles.

3. Task-Agnostic Vision-Language Pruning

In this section, we formally define the *Task-Agnostic Vision-Language Pruning* (TA-VLP) problem, discussing its challenges and its relation with prior work on pruning VLMs.

Preliminaries. Let f denote a VLM, and let $\Theta \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be its corresponding parameters after pretraining on a large-scale dataset \mathcal{D}_p of image-text pairs. Given data for a specific vision-language task t , we can fine-tune Θ to improve performance on t itself. While the standard practice is to directly update Θ , the latter is extremely high-dimensional and cannot always be stored. To circumvent this issue, pruning algorithms for VLMs [58] prune Θ explicitly for t . Formally, given task data \mathcal{D}_t , they aim at a binary mask $\mathbf{m}_t \in \mathbb{B}^n$, by maximizing a task-dependent criterion \mathcal{C}_t :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{m}_t = \arg \max_{\mathbf{m}} \mathcal{C}_t(f(\Theta \odot \mathbf{m}), \mathcal{D}_t) \\ \text{s.t. } \|\mathbf{m}\|_0 = k \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where k denotes the sparsity constraint (*i.e.*, the number of parameters to preserve). This mask should maximize the performance \mathfrak{p}_t of model f on task t , when f is trained using a given algorithm \mathcal{A}_t , *i.e.*, $\mathfrak{p}_t(\mathcal{A}_t, f, \Theta \odot \mathbf{m}_t)$. However, with this setup one needs to re-prune the model from scratch for every new task, which requires both time and storage of the original Θ . To overcome these issues, we shift the perspective towards task-agnostic model pruning.

Task-agnostic VLM Pruning. The goal of TA-VLP is to prune a VLM once while preserving trainability for arbitrary downstream tasks, without re-compressing the model from scratch. Formally, we aim for a task-agnostic mask \mathbf{m}_a that maximizes the performance of f on a series of *un-*

known downstream tasks \mathcal{T} :

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \mathfrak{p}_t(\mathcal{A}_t, f, \Theta \odot \mathbf{m}_a). \quad (2)$$

As it is unfeasible to collect data for *unknown* target tasks, a TA-VLP algorithm should produce \mathbf{m}_a from a generic dataset \mathcal{D}_g and a generic criterion \mathcal{C}_g , *i.e.*:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{m}_a = \arg \max_{\mathbf{m}} \mathcal{C}_g(f(\Theta \odot \mathbf{m}), \mathcal{D}_g) \\ \text{s.t. } \|\mathbf{m}\|_0 = k. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In this work, we always assume that \mathcal{D}_g is much smaller than the pretraining dataset \mathcal{D}_p , *i.e.*, $|\mathcal{D}_g| \ll |\mathcal{D}_p|$, as the aim of TA-VLP should not be to re-train a smaller model from scratch, but rather to efficiently prune an existing VLM. TA-VLP entails several challenges, as different tasks may exhibit stronger sensitivity to visual, textual, or fused knowledge. Intuitively, the solution to TA-VLP requires finding the optimal trade-off among modalities and encoded knowledge, respecting the priors of the pretrained VLM. In the following, we describe how we tackle TA-VLP by considering the multimodal information flow within VLMs.

4. MULTIFLOW: Multimodal Flow Pruning

In this section we introduce *Multimodal Flow Pruning*, a first algorithm for (unstructured) Task-Agnostic Vision-Language Pruning. We first discuss how we model the information flow within the VLM, and then how we exploit (multimodal) pretraining priors when pruning.

4.1. Modeling the Information Flow

As we lack task priors, we have one anchor when performing TA-VLP: the pretrained VLM. In fact, if we assume that the pretrained VLM encodes transferable representations, preserving how these representations emerge should maintain also the transferability to downstream tasks. We exploit this principle and tackle the problem from the perspective of the information flowing through the network, framing network pruning through the lens of message passing.

Without loss of generality, let us focus on a linear layer. We can represent a dense linear projection as a directed, weighted and complete bipartite graph $G = (L \cup R, E)$, where L and R are disjoint sets of nodes and E is the set of edges connecting them. Note that an edge $e_{lr} \in E$ connecting nodes $l \in L$ and $r \in R$ corresponds to a parameter $\theta_{lr} \in \Theta$. In this context, we model the importance of θ_{lr} as the information passing through its corresponding edge e_{lr} . This depends on three different values: (i) the weight of the edge, (ii) the saliency of the input node l , and (iii) the saliency of the output node r . In the following, we describe how we measure and combine these components.

Figure 2. MULTIFLOW. Orange trapezoids represent groups of parameters processing different modalities (i) To compute the **information flow** score for a parameter θ_{lr} , MULTIFLOW combines the importance of the **input neuron** l and that of **output neuron** r , aggregating them via the **local hop** from l to r through θ_{lr} . (ii) A **global saliency score** is obtained by computing (i) for all edges, and a **global modality-aware distribution** that exploits the emergent properties of large-scale pretraining guides layer-wise pruning.

Importance of an edge. This component is directly estimated from the absolute value of its corresponding weight, *i.e.*, $I(e_{lr}) = |\theta_{lr}|$, a simple and effective importance estimation technique well-known in the literature [18, 26]. Note that this measure inherently exploits pretraining information, as weight magnitudes can be viewed as long-term accumulators of movement in the parameter space as an emergent property from pretraining [56].

Saliency of a node. In each layer, input and output nodes have distinct roles: the former account for forwarding information, while the latter account for aggregating it. Given a vector $\mathbf{a}_l \in \mathbb{R}^N$ collecting N activations to an input node l of a given layer, we can anchor on the distinct roles of the neurons to assign ad-hoc saliency criteria. Following this intuition, we frame the saliency of $l \in L$ as the average strength of the signal it *emits* towards *all* output neurons:

$$S(l) = \frac{1}{|R|} \sum_{r \in R} \|\mathbf{a}_l\|_2 \cdot |\theta_{lr}|. \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, we treat the saliency of an output node $r \in R$ as the average strength of the signals it *receives*:

$$S(r) = \frac{1}{|L|} \sum_{l \in L} \|\mathbf{a}_l\|_2 \cdot |\theta_{lr}|. \quad (5)$$

Note that we use magnitude and norms to avoid potential sign misalignments between the two: those would create misleading importance scores as, *e.g.*, a negative weight with large magnitude may greatly influence the output and vice versa. To ensure that Eqs. (4) and (5) take into account both the modulation of the edges and the activation patterns

grounded in the VLM forward process, we estimate the activation norms over the available calibration data \mathcal{D}_g , similarly to concurrent work on LLM pruning [60]. Notably, this only requires forwarding \mathcal{D}_g through the model, which is much faster than also computing gradients.

Final score. Collating previous concepts, we define the saliency of each parameter θ_{lr} connecting nodes l and r via the edge e_{lr} , as the saliency of the path from l to r :

$$S(\theta_{lr}) = S(l) \cdot I(e_{lr}) \cdot S(r) = S(l) \cdot |\theta_{lr}| \cdot S(r). \quad (6)$$

Note that Eq. (6) equally balances the contribution of each graph part, involving both the information captured by the edge weights and its relation to the most salient nodes.

4.2. Multimodality-aware compression

Properly defining a saliency criterion ultimately enables ranking the parameters of a model and, consequently, network pruning. Given a target sparsity constraint k , the most straightforward solution would be to instantiate a binary mask preserving the top- k parameters according to the scores in Eq. (6). However, this would ignore potential sources of bias. For instance, as deeper layers accumulate magnitude from preceding ones, this may cause a large discrepancy in the scores, with the risk that the pruning criterion penalizes early layers and induces layer collapse [61]. This also applies to the multimodal nature of the model: as different layers may receive inputs from different modalities, by assuming that information equally flows among them, we may overlook their respective distribution, hence biasing our pruning mask on one of them. We provide more insights on both these phenomena in Sec. 6.

To avoid biasing the model towards a specific modality and/or network level, we re-weight the importance of each parameter based on the prior distribution given by the pre-trained VLM parameters. In fact, we found that the magnitude of the weights *detached* from the input/output information flow is a good indicator of the overall distribution that the pruned network should maintain layer-wise. This estimation tends to be more accurate if we keep into account which modality the layer processes, and its relevance increases with the disentanglement among modalities. Formally, given a layer ℓ processing information from modality m (e.g., visual or textual), with its corresponding parameters Θ_ℓ^m , we define its active parameter count k_ℓ^m as:

$$k_\ell^m = \sum_{\theta \in \Theta_\ell^m} \mathbb{1}(\theta \in \text{top}_k(|\cdot|, \Theta_\ell^m)) \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbb{1}$ is the indicator function and $\Theta^m \subset \Theta$ is the subset of parameters processing a specific modality m as input. $\text{top}_k(|\cdot|, \Theta^m)$ is the set of top- k elements in Θ^m if we rank elements according to their magnitude. Given this prior distribution k_ℓ^m , the final mask for the layer is:

$$\mathbf{m}_{l_r}^{\ell, m} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \theta_{l_r} \in \text{top}_{k_\ell^m}(S, \Theta_\ell^m) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

using S as criterion for the top_k . With Eq. (8), the compressed network will take into account: (i) the information flow (as estimated via Eq. (6)), (ii) the bias of the information at different levels of the network, and (iii) the peculiar flow of each modality (Eq. (7)). All this information, combined, allows the pruned model to maintain priors of the original model parameters and preserve core connections. The overall procedure of MULTIFLOW is depicted by Fig. 2.

5. Experiments

In this section, we benchmark well-established and recent pruning algorithms in TA-VLP. We experiment with three different downstream tasks: Image-Text Retrieval, Image-Captioning, and Visual Question Answering [13, 25, 42]. We additionally report Vision-only experiments in Sec. A.2.

Architectures. To study how distinct model designs impact TA-VLP, we experiment with two significantly different VLMs: BLIP_{BASE} [39], which uses a multimodal mixture of encoder-decoder networks, and XVLM_{CLIP}[71], where a vision-encoder and a text-encoder process information in parallel streams, with a final fusion encoder merging their output. While BLIP’s design is unique, many modern VLMs share the principles of modality separation (e.g., [53]) and fusion (e.g., [38, 40]) at the core of XVLM. For both, their vision encoders use 16×16 -sized patches.

Baselines. We compare to classical and recent approaches applicable to TA-VLP, divided between data-free and data-

driven methods. For data-free baselines, we include **One-shot Magnitude Pruning (OMP, [26])**, shown to outperform several state-of-the-art algorithms after training [19] and comparable to IMP for pretrained transformers [29]. We then include **LAMP [36]**, which extends OMP by unifying layer-wise calibration and global pruning. For data-driven methods, we choose two PaIs and two post-training pruning methods. Among PaIs, we select **SNIP [37]**, which retains connections based on their estimated impact on the loss function, and **ITERSNIP [52]** which gradually prunes by applying SNIP iteratively. For post-training pruning methods, we test **CHITA**, a recent state-of-the-art algorithm that relies on a low-rank decomposition of the Hessian matrix of the loss function [4], together with its iterative variant **CHITA++ [4]**. Additional baselines can be found in Sec. A.

Experimental setup. We test all pruning methods at 63% and 75% global sparsity for all tasks, choosing them to exceed trivial sparsities (i.e., $\leq 50\%$ [24]) and test in the neighborhood of the *essential sparsity* (i.e., the limit after which the performance drop always overcomes the sparsity gain [29], $\sim 70\%$). We study the extreme 90% sparsity in the next section. Data-dependent methods use the same set of calibration data on a *per-run* basis. To ensure no task-specific data is used for pruning, we construct \mathcal{D}_g from CC3M [57] and VisualGenome [31], and discard image-question pairs from the latter since they would collide with a portion of the data used for VQA finetuning. We sample $B = 3000$ batches from both datasets with a batch size of $b = 32$, totaling around $\sim 5\%$ of the standard 4M pretraining set for VLMs (\mathcal{D}_p) [50]. In this way, a critical requirement of TA-VLP is satisfied, i.e., $|\mathcal{D}_g| \ll |\mathcal{D}_p|$.

For first- and second-order methods, we use general-purpose pretraining losses, as defined in the original papers, excluding objectives that require fine-grained annotations not always available (i.e., visual grounding in XVLM). Note that these methods already have some form of task prior and are, thus, expected to outperform the others: for both XVLM and BLIP, the pretraining loss contains either all or a subset of the finetuning losses. For all downstream tasks, we fine-tune the pruned models with the same setup of the original papers and average the results over 3 runs with different seeds. We report additional details in the Appendix.

5.1. Image-Text Retrieval (ITR)

Setup. We evaluate all methods and architectures for Image-Text Retrieval (ITR) on MSCOCO [30], analyzing both Text-to-Image retrieval, where the model should pick a matching image from a pool of target ones given a textual query, and the specular task of Image-to-Text retrieval.

Results. Results are summarized in Tab. 1, where we report the established Image-Recall (IR) and Text-Recall (TR) metrics at different levels. MULTIFLOW outperforms prior methods at all image-grounded and text-grounded metrics,

Method	Sparsity	BLIP _{BASE}				XVLM _{CLIP}			
		Image-to-Text [%]		Text-to-Image [%]		Image-to-Text [%]		Text-to-Image [%]	
		R@1	R@5	R@1	R@5	R@1	R@5	R@1	R@5
DENSE	0%	80.72	95.08	62.99	85.27	78.18	94.48	60.94	84.41
RANDOM		0.02	0.12	0.02	0.10	21.48	46.66	14.89	37.61
SNIP		68.06±0.36	89.63±0.06	51.85±0.12	78.61±0.03	70.19±0.15	91.27±0.17	53.48±0.11	80.22±0.04
ITERSNIP*		0.03±0.01	0.14±0.04	0.02±0.00	0.10±0.01	67.12±1.33	89.18±0.94	50.78±0.89	78.63±0.60
OMP	63%	75.39±0.24	92.95±0.18	58.71±0.22	82.82±0.08	76.02±0.64	93.35±0.20	58.96±0.02	83.26±0.12
LAMP		70.36±0.12	90.49±0.20	53.83±0.21	79.62±0.16	75.32±0.21	93.27±0.13	58.38±0.31	83.17±0.09
CHITA		74.36±0.13	92.06±0.25	57.44±0.16	82.20±0.17	76.05±0.12	93.69±0.04	58.98±0.08	83.39±0.02
CHITA++		75.00±0.29	92.59±0.14	58.01±0.09	82.29±0.19	76.59±0.20	93.70±0.27	59.31±0.11	83.34±0.05
MULTIFLOW		76.31±0.09	93.27±0.10	59.02±0.09	83.08±0.10	77.35±0.51	93.75±0.04	60.21±0.16	83.99±0.05
RANDOM		0.06	0.08	0.05	0.14	12.18	30.98	8.63	24.35
SNIP		51.33±0.49	79.51±0.79	37.62±0.81	67.08±0.65	57.83±0.59	84.78±0.52	43.10±0.53	72.67±0.41
ITERSNIP*		0.03±0.01	0.12±0.07	0.04±0.03	0.14±0.07	46.16±0.84	76.13±0.89	33.52±0.51	64.14±0.56
OMP	75%	63.37±0.35	85.97±0.58	48.28±0.35	75.47±0.17	70.27±0.28	90.91±0.35	53.85±0.12	80.22±0.22
LAMP*		2.10±3.57	5.93±10.03	1.46±2.49	4.75±8.06	69.38±0.28	90.97±0.38	53.15±0.43	79.96±0.30
CHITA*		0.99±1.63	1.49±2.29	1.02±1.71	1.59±2.55	70.15±0.52	91.01±0.13	54.05±0.09	80.36±0.03
CHITA++		64.62±0.26	87.07±0.12	48.72±0.14	76.25±0.13	70.33±0.04	91.27±0.13	54.32±0.17	80.61±0.16
MULTIFLOW		65.73±0.60	87.97±0.52	49.85±0.59	77.18±0.45	73.87±0.13	92.91±0.23	56.94±0.10	82.29±0.07

Table 1. Results for Image-Text Retrieval on COCO at 63% and 75% sparsity. The dense BLIP and XVLM upper bounds are reported on top. For further context, we include the random baseline as the lower bound. The **best performer** is bold; the second best is underlined. The superscript * denotes algorithms that perform comparably to the random baseline when pruning BLIP.

at all sparsity levels, and for all models. With XVLM, the gap between MULTIFLOW and the second best increases with the sparsity: at 63% sparsity, MULTIFLOW outperforms CHITA++ by +0.76% and +0.90% on TR@1 and IR@1 respectively, up to +3.54% and +2.62% when the overall sparsity increases to 75%. When pruning BLIP, MULTIFLOW remains the best performer while OMP becomes the second best method, outperforming CHITA++ at the lower sparsity. In general, performance drops with BLIP are much larger than those of XVLM, with 3 out of 7 methods (denoted by *) performing comparably to the random baseline. This hints at the following: *given a fixed task, different VLMs expose different "prunabilities"*. Beyond the comparison between MULTIFLOW and the state-of-the-art, these experiments unveil another important finding: *general purpose knowledge is retained by most methods*. This observation is signaled by the TR@5 and IR@5 metrics, where the performance drop is contained regardless of the algorithm.

5.2. Image Captioning (IC)

Setup. Image Captioning (IC) is the task of generating a text given a source image (and a prompt in VLMs). We employ COCO Captions to evaluate the pruned models for this task [13]. Following [39, 71], during fine-tuning both BLIP and XVLM optimize a language-modeling loss and use the prompt "a picture of". For quantitative evaluation, we use the standard BLEU@4 [51] and CIDEr [64] scores. We report METEOR [3] and SPICE [2] in the Appendix.

Results. The outcome of this experiment is reported in Tab. 2. Notably, a pattern observed in ITR is confirmed also for IC: with XVLM, the gap between MULTIFLOW and the second best performing algorithm increases with the sparsity (+0.50% BLEU@4 and +2.46 CIDEr at 63% becoming

+1.06% and +4.47 at 75% sparsity). When pruning BLIP, MULTIFLOW and CHITA++ perform equally well, with an edge for MULTIFLOW at 63% sparsity and the opposite at 75%. Importantly, we make a key observation: for both ITR and IC, *there is no fixed second best*. Different algorithms overcome each other when changing either the target model or sparsity. This further underlines the importance of designing *ad-hoc* methods for TA-VLP.

5.3. Visual Question Answering (VQA)

Setup. VQA requires the model to answer a question by analyzing the content of an associated image. The training set for the task collates the train and validation splits from the VQA2.0 dataset [25], and the image-question pairs from Visual Genome [31], as customary in the field. Given that generative capabilities are implicitly embodied by IC, with VQA we focus on the *analytical capabilities* of the pruned models. Thus, we evaluate closed-set VQA, and let pruned models choose from a predefined set of 3129 answers [38].

Results. We evaluate all methods against the official evaluation website and provide results in Tab. 2. VQA evaluation confirms the patterns: MULTIFLOW is the best performer in 3 out of 4 instances. Within these 4 instances, we emphasize the further absence of a fixed second-best method: (1) OMP is the second best with BLIP at 63% sparsity; (2) at the same level, CHITA and CHITA++ perform on par as the second best with XVLM; (3) at 75% MULTIFLOW lies less than one standard deviation below the best performer CHITA++ and (4) the latter underperforms the proposed method by -0.81% with XVLM. These results disclose a complementary finding to Sec. 5.1: not only VLMs, but also *vision-language tasks expose different prunabilities*. In the next section, we further investigate both phenomena.

Method	Sparsity	BLIP _{BASE}			XVLM _{CLIP}		
		VQA	Image Captioning		VQA	Image Captioning	
		<i>test-dev</i>	BLEU@4	CIDEr	<i>test-dev</i>	BLEU@4	CIDEr
DENSE	0%	76.31	39.10	131.14	76.92	38.99	130.43
RANDOM		54.22	15.88	38.54	61.48	23.73	69.00
SNIP		71.66±0.07	36.52±0.01	117.46±0.26	72.62±1.45	37.30±0.39	122.98±0.82
ITERSNIP		63.26±0.01	26.57±0.10	75.80±0.26	72.92±0.14	36.52±0.16	120.12±0.52
OMP	63%	<u>73.59±0.04</u>	37.36±0.07	124.86±0.27	75.16±0.94	<u>37.97±0.09</u>	<u>126.13±0.12</u>
LAMP		72.16±0.01	35.96±0.02	119.23±0.03	75.37±0.03	37.83±0.18	125.74±0.29
CHITA		73.34±0.06	37.26±0.06	124.76±0.18	75.82±0.04	37.82±0.20	125.75±0.57
CHITA++		73.52±0.03	37.52±0.05	125.54±0.10	75.82±0.08	37.71±0.11	125.44±0.54
MULTIFLOW		73.74±0.08	37.74±0.17	125.40±0.29	76.02±0.03	38.47±0.01	128.59±0.13
RANDOM		51.78	13.37	30.16	58.68	20.51	56.35
SNIP		67.07±0.13	33.5±0.21	101.29±0.62	69.77±0.03	34.29±0.27	110.22±1.41
ITERSNIP		52.28±0.10	14.35±0.23	29.88±0.28	67.11±0.08	31.15±0.32	98.24±1.74
OMP	75%	69.41±0.07	34.92±0.05	113.77±0.24	73.48±0.07	35.74±0.09	118.37±0.29
LAMP		63.33±0.78	28.2±0.08	88.25±0.12	73.22±0.02	36.34±0.01	120.13±0.13
CHITA		69.08±0.02	35.13±0.07	114.11±0.14	73.44±0.02	35.98±0.39	119.12±1.05
CHITA++		70.13±0.05	35.77±0.07	116.97±0.14	74.00±0.01	36.07±0.04	119.48±0.16
MULTIFLOW		<u>70.09±0.03</u>	<u>35.73±0.10</u>	<u>116.31±0.13</u>	74.81±0.06	37.40±0.06	124.60±0.08

Table 2. Results on VQA2.0 and COCO Captions at 63% and 75% sparsity. The dense BLIP and XVLM upper bounds are reported on top. For further context, we include the random baseline as the lower bound. The best performer is bold; the second best is underlined.

6. Additional Analyses

6.1. Extreme sparsity and different prunability

In Sec. 5, we report results at 63% and 75% sparsity, revealing that different VLMs and vision-language tasks exhibit inherently different prunabilities. Here, we verify if these observations remain valid at 90% global sparsity, an extreme compression level where performance reliable for real-world applications has not yet been reached in VLM pruning. All of these experiments are depicted in Fig. 3.

VLMs are not equally prunable. Results in Fig. 3 convey a strong message: even if identically pruned and similar in total parameter counts, every pruned BLIP model underperforms the corresponding pruned XVLM although starting from a generally better or comparable dense performance. No method can produce meaningful results when pruning BLIP at 90% sparsity regardless of the task, with all methods failing in ITR (*i.e.*, $R@1 \leq 1\%$) and being almost on par with the random baseline in VQA and IC. We hypothesize that parameters integrating different modalities are a key aspect to preserve, and that the explicit disentanglement among vision, text, and fusion modalities within XVLM makes it less sensitive to parameter removal. Here, MULTIFLOW outperforms CHITA++, the average second best, by +6.93, +10.14, and +24.88 in VQA-acc, BLEU@4, and TR@1, respectively, while also being 41× faster on average, (see Tab. 7 in Appendix C). We believe this is a great leap forward in pruning VLMs to extreme sparsities.

Algorithms rank differently across settings. The observation that *no fixed second best* is present at 63% and 75% sparsities also remains valid at 90%. For example, LAMP outperforms SNIP in ITR, while the opposite happens in IC. This hints at the fact that pruning algorithms preserve dif-

ferent types of encoded knowledge and further underlines the effectiveness of the task-agnostic design of MULTIFLOW which steadily maintains good performance across tasks, outperforming all competitors in all tasks for XVLM.

VL tasks can be ranked by difficulty. The *prune-then-transfer* paradigm leads to extreme differences in how performance drops according to the downstream task. With XVLM, the gaps between the dense upper bound and the best performer MULTIFLOW are \downarrow TR@1 \sim 40% and \downarrow IR@1 \sim 43% for ITR, but jump to only \downarrow *test-dev-acc* \sim 12% and \downarrow BLEU@4 \sim 20% for VQA and IC. While this may highlight different sensitivities among metrics, it also enables ranking the tasks as VQA < IC < ITR in terms of their difficulty, hinting that a good algorithm for TA-VLP shall emphasize image-text alignment.

6.2. Ablations and sanity checks on MULTIFLOW

In this section we perform two ablation studies of MULTIFLOW, testing the performance of the inverted mask, and ablating the impact of the imposed distribution.

Inversion. Inspired by [19], we check if the saliency function at the core of a score-based pruning algorithm effectively extracts the most important weights, by inverting the mask and maintaining the parameters with the lowest scores. Tab 3 shows that the score in MULTIFLOW successfully does so: inverting the pruning mask even extracts subnetworks that perform far *worse* than the random baseline.

Imposed distribution. Here we test the impact of the imposed multimodal prior described in Sec. 4.2 on MULTIFLOW, replacing it with two variants (i) not imposing a prior distribution on the layer-wise pruning ratios (*i.e.*, the mask is computed taking the top-k global scores), (ii) determining the layer-wise pruning ratios according to the weight

Figure 3. Experiments at 90% sparsity. ITR with XVLM (left) - VQA with both BLIP and XVLM (center) - IC with both BLIP and XVLM (right). The **random** and **dense** baselines are also reported. All experiments follow the same configuration as those of Tabs. 1 and 2.

Ablation	Sparsity	Text R@1	Image R@1
RANDOM		21.48	14.89
MULTIFLOW w/ Inversion		7.15	5.16
MULTIFLOW w/o distribution	63%	0.01±0.01	0.02±0.0
MULTIFLOW w/o multimodality		76.66±0.09	59.96±0.20
MULTIFLOW		77.35	60.21
RANDOM		12.18	8.63
MULTIFLOW w/ Inversion		1.91	0.88
MULTIFLOW w/o distribution	75%	0.02±0.0	0.01±0.01
MULTIFLOW w/o multimodality		72.50±0.05	55.75±0.12
MULTIFLOW		73.87	56.94
RANDOM		2.92	1.93
MULTIFLOW w/ Inversion		0.43	0.20
MULTIFLOW w/o distribution	90%	0.02±0.0	0.03±0.01
MULTIFLOW w/o multimodality		35.55±0.26	25.00±0.06
MULTIFLOW		46.87	34.77

Table 3. Ablation study on ITR and MSCOCO (XVLM). Both the **inversion** and the **imposed distribution** studies are reported.

magnitude. These distributions are displayed in Fig. 4 for different parts of the model (*i.e.*, vision, text, fusion), and with corresponding performance on ITR in Tab. 3. As we can see from Fig. 4, without imposing any prior distribution (blue line), the model would either heavily prune early layers (*e.g.*, vision) or full modalities (*e.g.*, text), resulting in performance even worse than random due to model collapse (Tab. 3). The magnitude-based distribution (*i.e.*, w/o multimodality) already recovers this effect, with a more distributed pruning across layers and modalities. However, including multimodal priors leads to the best results, especially at 90% sparsity (*e.g.*, +11% on TR@1, +9% on IR@1). This experiment discloses two final findings: (i) considering potential biases in activation patterns among layers and modalities is fundamental for VLM pruning and (ii) in high-sparsity regimes, a small shift in the layer-wise distribution can correspond to a large performance gap.

7. Conclusions

In this work, we formalized and addressed *Task-Agnostic Vision-Language Pruning* (TA-VLP). We proposed Multi-modal Flow Pruning (MULTIFLOW), an approach that preserves the information flow within the original VLM by ex-

Figure 4. Comparison of the sparsities obtained at each layer ℓ of each modality by (i) pruning with the **topk** global scores of MULTIFLOW (denoted by *w/o distribution*), (ii) OMP (*w/o multimodality*) and (iii) MULTIFLOW. The figure displays XVLM.

ploiting a (multimodal) prior on the weight magnitude for layer-wise pruning, and by incorporating the saliencies of input/output nodes into the scoring criterion for network parameters. We also benchmarked 8 pruning methods for TA-VLP, using two VLMs, three vision-language tasks, and different pruning ratios, showing that MULTIFLOW outperforms existing state-of-the-art methods in the vast majority of the cases. While our results highlight a large gap between the dense model and its pruned counterpart, this work is a step toward finding task-agnostic pruned VLMs.

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